

IMPROVING THE OPTIMIZED MECHANISM FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF LOGISTICS SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada transport xizmatlarini yanada rivojlantirishda raqamli iqtisodiyotning o'rni va raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalansh yo'nalishlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, transport xizmatlari, avtomobil transport, temir yo'l transporti, havo transporti, yuk tashish transporti.

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается роль цифровой экономики в дальнейшем развитии транспортных услуг и направления использования цифровых технологий.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, транспортные услуги, автомобильный транспорт, железнодорожный транспорт, воздушный транспорт, грузовой транспорт.

Abstract. This article describes the role of the digital economy in the further development of transport services and the directions of using digital technologies.

Keywords: digital economy, transport services, road transport, railway transport, air transport, freight transport.

Introduction

In the digital economy, efficiency, speed, and cost optimization in logistics are of paramount importance. The quality of service can be improved by automating logistics processes and improving management systems using modern technologies (AI, IoT, blockchain, big data analytics).

Digital logistics is not just the introduction of technologies, but also the restructuring of the entire business model. Companies, using solutions such as AI, IoT, blockchain, not only increase their efficiency, but also ensure their competitiveness in the market. To develop digital logistics systems in Uzbekistan:

- Joint state projects (for example, "Smart Transport System").
- Support for startups and innovative ideas.
- Use of international experience

In order to further develop the provision of motor transport services in the digital economy, achieve comprehensive socio-economic development of regions, strengthen the role of motor transport services in solving the problems of population employment in cities and villages of the country, increase passenger transportation safety, reduce harmful emissions into the atmosphere, and further develop passenger transportation by motor transport in the republic, the following have been established:

1. Ensuring a more complete satisfaction of the population's demand for car transportation by updating the fleet with modern, comfortable buses and minibuses, rationally organizing and expanding routes, and improving road surfaces, primarily in rural areas;

2. Strengthening passenger transportation safety measures, ensuring strict adherence to route schedules, improving the quality of services provided, forming a system for protecting consumer rights in the passenger transportation sector, and introducing a cashless payment system for fares;

3. Ensuring rational and efficient use of buses and minibuses, strengthening the financial and economic situation of road transport enterprises;

4 The passenger transportation management system should make extensive use of modern information and communication technologies.

Today, the following types of transport services have been formed in our republic, including:

- road transport services;

- railway transport services;
- pipeline transport services;
- air transport services;
- auxiliary transport activities and others.

Figure 1. Cargo turnover in Kashkadarya region (mln. t.)¹

As can be seen from the above data, in 2023, the city of Karshi in the Kashkadarya region achieved high results in terms of cargo turnover. The research conducted shows that in the current era of rapid development of the digital economy, we give the following conclusions and recommendations for the further development of transport services using digital technologies. 1 Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2724 dated January 10, 2017 Firstly, to develop a unified transport system, seamlessly connecting all types of transport, to

¹ <https://www.qashstat.uz>

create the possibility of getting to and from the destination based on daily transport services between major cities;

Secondly, to increase the mobility of the population in intercity travel through the development of air transport;

Thirdly, by creating a network of transport and logistics centers, taking into account the main points of cargo formation in the regions;

Fourth, the gradual transition of transport documents for international cargo transportation ("e-Permit", "eTIR", "e-CMR") to electronic format and the reduction of freight costs by up to 30 percent; Fifth, the improvement of a single electronic portal that provides for the sale of electronic tickets for air, railway and intercity, interregional buses; Sixth, by introducing an electronic portal that displays analytical and statistical data on the transport sector, in our opinion, we can achieve very good results by digitizing transport services in the republic.

By implementing digital logistics mechanisms, companies can increase their competitiveness, use resources efficiently, and adapt to modern business requirements. It is clear that the use of technological innovations, staff training, and investments in system integration will dramatically increase efficiency in the logistics sector. Digital transformation will take logistics services to a new level, benefiting not only businesses but the entire economy. Digital transformation is making logistics faster, cheaper, and more reliable. Companies can strengthen their market position by investing in new technologies.

Conclusion

To summarize, it is clear that not all organizations engaged in logistics activities in the digital economy can quickly adapt their work to the digital services market and successfully compete in it. Today, there is an increasing need to have tools for interacting with electronic trading intermediaries (Internet exchanges, online trading platforms). Also, in the digital economy, logistics efficiency management mechanisms play an important role in increasing the competitiveness of companies and improving customer service. The introduction of modern technologies such as big data, the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence and blockchain allows you to optimize logistics processes, improve demand forecasting, reduce costs and increase supply reliability. In the current period and in the near future, the introduction of promising developments such as digital infrastructure and intermodal services in the transport system of our country will significantly increase the volume of passenger and freight transportation and have a significant impact on economic stability. This is because our country has a favorable geographical and transit location. Considering that we do not have waterways and transport is only on land, the importance of railways and road transport in our country will naturally increase, and the problems that arise will have to be eliminated.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 10-yanvardagi PQ-2724-son qarori www.lex.uz
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.Mirziyoyev tomonidan tasdiqlangan “2022-2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi” 2022-yil 28-yanvar. // www.lex.uz
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020 yil 5 oktyabrdagi ““Raqamli O‘zbekiston - 2030” strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish choratadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PF-6079-sonli Farmoni // www.lex.uz

3. Воеводко Юрий. Как «хотелки» покупателей приводят к цифровой трансформации логистических цепей, и что поможет их выполнить [Электронный ресурс]. – режим доступа: https://newretail.ru/business/kak_khotelki_pokupateley_privodyat_k_tsifrovoy_transformatsii_logisticheski_kh_tsepey_i_chno_pomozhet/. (дата обращения: 05.03.2020)
4. Рожко, О. Н. Трансформация национального рынка логистических услуг в условиях цифровой экономики / О. Н. Рожко, В. В. Хоменко // Проблемы современной экономики. – 2019. – № 3 (71). – С. 211–215. 3. Королёва, А. А. Экономические эффекты цифровой логистики / А. А. Королёва // Журнал Бел. гос. ун-та. Экономика. – 2019. – № 1. – С. 68–76.
5. Дыбская В.В., Сергеев В.И. Цифровая логистика и управление цепями поставок: перспективы развития. [Электронный ресурс]. – режим доступа: http://ea.donntu.org:8080/bitstream/123456789/33474/1/conf_res1_12-13_04_18.pdf. (дата обращения: 05.03.2020)